

Kinetics and Mechanism of Copper(II)-catalysed Oxidation of Asparagine by Sodium *N*-Chloro-*p*-toluenesulphonamide in Alkaline Media

SATISH KUMAR SINGH SENGAR* and B. S. YADAV

Chemical Research Laboratories, R. B. S. College, Agra-282 002

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The kinetics of the Cu^{II}-catalysed chloraminometric oxidation of asparagine have been investigated in aqueous NaOH. The reaction rate is first order in chloramine-T and asparagine concentration and inverse first order in hydroxide ion concentration. The profile obtained from plots of observed rate constant against Cu^{II} ion concentration, indicates that the oxidation reaction proceeds through both uncatalysed and catalysed pathways. A negligible salt-effect and solvent-effect point to a mechanism involving a neutral molecule and anion in rate-determining step. The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters have been computed and suitable rate laws consistent with the experimental findings have been deduced.

EXTENSIVE studies have been made on amino acids owing to their importance in biochemistry.

The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of amino acids by chloramine-T have been reported¹⁻⁴. The biological significance of catalytic function of Cu^{II} and its complex forming nature during amino acid metabolism⁵ has fascinated chemists to know the mechanistic aspects of Cu^{II}-catalysed chloraminometric oxidation of amino acids. However, a few reports pertaining to such studies have been brought out recently⁶⁻¹¹. The present paper describes the results of kinetics of oxidation of asparagine (Asn) by chloramine-T (CAT) in alkaline medium with the catalytic action of copper(II) ions.

Experimental

An aqueous stock solution of chloramine-T (E. Merck, G.R.) was standardised iodometrically^{1,2}. The solution of asparagine (B.D.H.) was always prepared afresh in double-distilled water. All other reagents employed were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout the experiments.

Kinetic measurements: The pseudo-first order conditions were maintained in all kinetic runs, i.e. [Asparagine] \gg [Chloramine-T]. A solution containing the requisite amounts of asparagine, copper sulphate, alkali and water (to keep the total volume constant throughout) was equilibrated at 45° and to it a measured quantity of chloramine-T solution (pre-equilibrate at same temperature) was added rapidly. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the unconsumed CAT present in measured aliquot of the reaction mixture at regular time intervals using iodometric methods^{1,2}. The rate constant values were calculated directly from the integrated formula for first order reactions. The

reaction was also studied in presence of different neutral salts such as NaNO₃, KNO₃ and K₂SO₄, and the strength was adjusted to 1–3 × 10⁻² M. For the determination of activation parameters, the reaction was studied at four different temperatures.

Stoichiometry and products: The stoichiometry of reaction was determined under pseudo-first order conditions ([Asn] \gg [CAT]) by equilibrate varying ratios of chloramine-T to asparagine concentration at room temperature (\approx 27°) for 144 h. The results indicate that 1 mol of asparagine reacts with 2 mol of chloramine-T.

α -Cyanoacetamide has been confirmed as the reaction end-product by conventional analytical methods^{1,2}. Dakin^{1,4} also reported that when 1 mol of amino acid consumes 2 mol of chloramine-T in the reaction, nitriles are the final products. Asparagine may undergo oxidation in accordance with the following steps,

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the pseudo-first order rate constants for Cu^{II}-catalysed oxidation of asparagine by sodium *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulphonamide at 45°. At constant concentration of asparagine and sodium hydroxide, the plots of log [Chloramine-T] vs time

TABLE 1—EFFECTS OF [REACTANT], [NaOH] AND [CATALYST] ON RATE OF OXIDATION OF ASPARAGINE BY CHLORAMINE-T AT 45°

[CAT] × 10 ³ M	[Asn] × 10 ² M	[NaOH] × 10 ² M	[Cu ^{II}] × 10 ³ M	k'_1 × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	$k'_1/[Asn]$ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$k'_1 \times [NaOH]$ × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹ mol
0.6	1.0	4.0	2.0	5.47	—	—
0.8	1.0	4.0	2.0	5.52	—	—
1.0	1.0	4.0	2.0	5.74	—	—
1.2	1.0	4.0	2.0	5.53	—	—
1.4	1.0	4.0	2.0	5.82	—	—
1.0	0.8	4.0	2.0	4.72	5.90	—
1.0	1.0	4.0	2.0	5.76	5.76	—
1.0	1.2	4.0	2.0	6.92	5.76	—
1.0	1.4	4.0	2.0	7.95	5.68	—
1.0	1.6	4.0	2.0	9.24	5.77	—
1.0	1.0	2.4	2.0	9.28	—	2.22
1.0	1.0	3.2	2.0	6.68	—	2.03
1.0	1.0	4.0	2.0	5.76	—	2.20
1.0	1.0	4.8	2.0	4.70	—	2.25
1.0	1.0	5.6	2.0	3.88	—	2.17
1.0	1.0	4.0	1.2	4.28	—	—
1.0	1.0	4.0	1.6	5.03	—	—
1.0	1.0	4.0	2.0	5.74	—	—
1.0	1.0	4.0	2.4	6.43	—	—
1.0	1.0	4.0	2.8	7.05	—	—

were linear and the rate constant was found to be independent of initial concentration of chloramine-T. Thus, it is indicative that the reaction follows a first order dependence in chloramine-T concentration. At constant concentrations of chloramine-T and sodium hydroxide, the reaction rate increased with increase in asparagine concentration. The rate decreased with the increase in OH⁻ concentration at constant concentrations of chloramine-T and asparagine. The concordant values of factors $k'_1/[Asn]$ and $k'_1 \times [NaOH]$ confirm the first order in asparagine concentration and inverse first order in sodium hydroxide concentration, respectively. Moreover, the reaction rate is also increased with the increase in catalyst, copper sulphate concentration with constant concentration of other reactants. The plots of rate constant vs Cu^{II} ion concentration are linear with non-zero intercept on rate constant axis, indicating both uncatalysed and catalysed reactions taking place simultaneously.

The variation in ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium has no effect on the reaction rate. The dielectric constant of the medium was varied by adding increasing proportion of the methanol to the reaction mixture. In order to compute the thermodynamic parameters, the reaction was studied at four different temperatures (Table 2). Plots of log k'_1 vs absolute temperature are linear and energy of activation (E^*) calculated from the

slope which comes out to be 17.29 kcal mol⁻¹. Other thermodynamic parameters were also determined for the oxidation reaction. The values are $\Delta S^\ddagger = -22.51$ e.u., $\Delta H^\ddagger = 16.64$ kcal mole⁻¹, $\Delta F^\ddagger = 23.82$ kcal mol⁻¹.

Chloramine-T in aqueous solution of NaOH hydrolyses to *p*-toluenesulphochloramide and *p*-toluenesulphonamide,

The possible oxidising species of alkaline solution of CAT are CAT itself, CAT' and NaClO. If CAT itself was to be the reactive oxidising species, the rate should have been first order with respect to sodium hydroxide concentration, which is contrary to the experimental observations. Thus, either CAT' or NaClO is the oxidising species of chloramine-T which reacts with the substrate. In alkaline medium, asparagine is present in the anionic form and, therefore, its interaction with ClO⁻ is ruled out based on salt-effect studies, because such an interaction would result a positive salt-effect. Evidently the active species is *p*-toluenesulphochloramide (CAT'). The following mechanism has been proposed.

Copper(II) ion added to the reaction mixture forms the complex with the asparagine anion^{15,16} and there is an equilibrium between the complexed and uncomplexed ions,

hydrolysis of chloramine-T occurs as

TABLE 2—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR Cu^{II}-CATALYSED CHLORAMINE-T OXIDATION OF ASPARAGINE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

$k'_1 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	Temp. (°C)			
	40.0	45.0	50.0	55.0
	3.61	5.74	9.58	14.58

The active species CAT' reacts in the slow step with uncomplexed and complexed asparagine ions as

In step (4), catalyst Cu^{II} is regenerated. X is monochloramino acetate ion formed as an intermediate which further reacts with another CAT' molecule to yield the products,

The rate expression for the consumption of chloramine-T is derived by applying the steady state treatment to all the intermediate formed during the reaction course. Thus

$$-d[\text{CAT}]/dt = k_1[\text{CAT}][\text{H}_2\text{O}] - k_{-1}[\text{CAT}'][\text{NaOH}] \quad (A)$$

Further, on applying steady state treatment to steps (2-5) and making the following assumptions. Water is in a large excess and, therefore, [H₂O] remains constant throughout the reaction (2). $k_2[\text{Asn}^-] \ll k_{-1}[\text{NaOH}]$. The following rate expression (B) is obtained,

$$\frac{k_1[\text{CAT}][\text{H}_2\text{O}] - k_{-1}[\text{CAT}'][\text{NaOH}]}{= 2k_2[\text{Asn}^-][\text{CAT}'] + 2k_3[\text{Cu-Asn}][\text{CAT}']} \quad (B)$$

Therefore, from (A) and (B) we get,

$$-d[\text{CAT}]/dt = 2\{k_2[\text{Asn}^-][\text{CAT}'] + k_3[\text{Cu-Asn}][\text{CAT}']\} \quad (C)$$

Value of [CAT'] obtained from step (2) is fed into expression (C) to get,

$$-d[\text{CAT}]/dt = \frac{2k_1}{k_{-1}} \frac{[\text{CAT}][\text{NaOH}]}{\{k_2[\text{Asn}^-] + k_3[\text{Cu-Asn}]\}} \quad (D)$$

from step (1),

$$[\text{Cu-Asn}] = K_{\text{eq}} [\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{Asn}^-] \quad (E)$$

This value of [Cu-Asn] is fed into expression (D) to get,

$$-d[\text{CAT}]/dt = \frac{2k_1k_2}{k_{-1}} \frac{[\text{CAT}][\text{Asn}^-]}{[\text{NaOH}]} \left\{ 1 + \frac{k_3K_{\text{eq}}}{k_2} [\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] \right\} \quad (F)$$

Therefore, the catalysed reaction's rate constant k'_1 is comprised of

$$k'_1 = \frac{2k_1k_2}{k_{-1}} + \frac{2k_1k_3K_{\text{eq}}}{k_{-1}}$$

The expression (F) shows linear dependence of reaction rate on Cu^{II} ion concentration.

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